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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

BIRTH OF A SIBYL: THE MEDIEVAL CONNECTION¹

PART 2

14. The astounding journey from Famurgan to the Apennine Sibyl

In the previous chapter, we saw that an unexpected connection was established, in the year 1185, between Morgan le Fay, a main character within the Arthurian chivalric cycle, and one of the classical Sibyls: they were both considered as supreme sorcerers, able to communicate with the Netherworld and its demons, and provide oracular responses, even by means of necromancy, an impious and forbidden craft. And both were

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associated to Erictho, the hideous witch of ancient Greece described by first-century author Marcus Annaeus Lucanus in his “Pharsalia”.

This connection, previously overlooked though known to scholars, is contained in “Erec”, a chivalric poem written by Hartmann von Aue, a German knight and poet.

What is the relevance of all this, if any, to our search into the enigma of the true origin of the legendary tale about an Apennine Sibyl?

Can we suppose that some of the dark, sinister traits concerning the new Morgan le Fay, originally a benign prophetess and healer and now turned into a witch and necromancer after Hartmann von Aue's “Erec”, might have been transferred, through the centuries and by a tradition which is both oral and literary, to another gloomy figure, that of an Apennine Sibyl?

Fig. 51 - «Sibilla» and «Famurgan» as they appear in Hartmann von Aue's *Erec* (Folium 40v of Codex Vindobonensis Ser. Nova 2663 *Ambraser Heldenbuch*)

Can we really make the challenging assumption that the Apennine Sibyl only represents a further extraneous layer, another chivalric artifact which screens the true nature of the inner core of the legendary tale about the Sibillini Mountain Range in Italy?

Can we daringly push ourselves as far as to conjecture that the legendary figure of Morgan le Fay has been transplanted and adapted to the Italian Apennines, creating in this way, from what it might appear as a misty, unfathomable void, the myth of an Apennine Sibyl?

The narrow path we are going to follow is truly staggering and dumbfounding. However, we will see that the very same conclusions we are about to draw, on an independent basis and bewildering as they might appear, were also reached many years ago by one of the greatest American scholars on the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle, Roger Sherman Loomis.

But let's start from Hartmann von Aue's twelfth century, and search across the subsequent hundreds of years for further clues which might provide an increasing evidence of a close relationship between Morgan le Fay, the Sibyls, and the Apennine Sibyl.

Let's unfold another heavy, opaque layer of the shield which covers the most genuine essence of the Sibyl of the Apennines.

15. Morgan le Fay, an enchanted mountain, a place for blissful joy

We are now about to start from Morgan le Fay and move on through chivalric literature: there, at the very end of our path, we will behold the looming, sinister figure of the Apennine Sibyl.

Our first step moves from one of the masterpieces of German chivalric literature: the poem *Parzival*, written by Wolfram von Eschenbach at the beginning of the thirteenth century, around twenty years after Hartmann von Aue's *Erec*. We are going to find significant traces of Morgan le Fay in one of the most complete manuscripts bearing the poem's text: manuscript no. 857 preserved in the Stiftsbibliothek, the Library Hall of the benedictine abbey of St. Gall, Switzerland, and dating to around 1260.

And what do we find in *Parzival*? Again, we find Famorgan, or Morgan le Fay. And, for the first time, King Arthur's half-sister is mentioned in association with something new, a most significant feature, of a kind that

had never been referenced before in Morgan's literary tradition: an enchanted mountain.

It happens in Chapter VIII, verse 400.8, when the knight Gawain encounters another knight, King Vergulaht:

«Mazadan sent forth his [Vergulaht's] family - from the mountain of Famorgan - his origin was from the fays» (in the original Old German text: «sin geslaechte sante Mazadan - fur den berch ce Famorgan - sîn art was von der feien»).

Fig. 52 - The association between Morgan the Fay and a mountain as it appears in Folium 115 of manuscript no. 857 (*Parzival*) preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of St. Gall's Abbey, Switzerland

And later in the epic, in Chapter IX, verse 496-8, the same association between Morgan le Fay and a mountain is stated once more, when another knight speaks as follows:

«I have also engaged in many knightly combats before the mountain of Famorgan» (in the original Old German text: «Ich hân ouch manege tjust getan vor dem berch ze Famorgan»).

Fig. 53 - The mountain of Famorgan from Folium 142 of manuscript no. 857 (*Parzival*) preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of St. Gall's Abbey, Switzerland

Thus not only Morgan is associated with a charmed island, that of Avalon, as reported by Geoffrey of Monmouth in his works *Vita Merlini* and *Historia Regum Britanniae*, dating to the first half of the twelfth century and referring to an antique tradition: now, for the first time ever, we find a literary mention in which a relationship between Morgan le Fay and a special, enchanted mountain is established. It is «dem berch ze Famorgan». With Wolfram von Eschenbach's *Parzival*, a small, significant step towards an evil fay living on or beneath a mountainous cliff has been taken.

Is that all? No, because *Parzival* hides a further clue which brings us closer to an Apennine Sibyl.

In two further passages (Chapter I, verse 56.19 and Chapter XII, verse 585.15), Morgan le Fay is associated to a most significant attribute, a magical “Land of Bliss”:

«King Mazadan was their father - a fay led the king to Morgan - her name was Land-of-joy / [...] When Mazadan was king - who was brought to Morgan le Fay by Land-of-joy» (in the original Old German text: «der zweier vatr hiez Mazadan - den fuort ein feie in Morgan - diu hiez Terre de lascoye / [...] Sît her von Mazadane - den ze Famurgane - Terre delascoye fuorte - den iwer chraft do ruorte»).

Fig. 54 - Morgan's Land-of-Joy mentioned in Folium 20 (above) and Folium 166 (below) of manuscript no. 857 (*Parzival*) preserved at the Stiftsbibliothek of St. Gall's Abbey, Switzerland

So not only Morgan le Fay is connected to a mountain, she is also linked to a magical land where pleasure and bliss seem to rule. Though Wolfram von Eschenbach seems to attach the name «Land-of-joy» to a fay, most scholars believe that this is a mistaken reference to Avalon, the magical land, the «Blessed Isle» in the definition originally set down by Geoffrey of Monmouth.

In any case, something is slowly changing in the figure and traits of Morgan le Fay: from a benign healer living in a heavenly island, to a powerful witch and necromancer, a fay referenced in association with a mountain and a place of blissful joy.

An association that - we must not forget - is also stated in another thirteenth-century chivalric romance, *Floriant et Florète*, which we already saw in a previous article. In this poem, we found Morgan le Fay as the inhabitant of Mongibel, or Mount Etna, in southern Italy:

«Three fairies coming from the see - Their master is called - Morgan, King Arthur's sister - [...] and then took their way back, - towards Mongibel they headed - where their castle lay [...] - Know then, by your own eyes and with no lies - That this castle of Mongibel is enchanted - Know that the truth is as follows: - No one can ever die here».

[In the original Old French text: «Trois fées de la mer salée - La mestresse d'aux ert nommée - Morgain, la suer le roi Artu - [...] Aitant s'en tornernet, - Vers Mongibel s'acheminèrent - Quar c'estoit lor mestre chastel [...] - Sachiez de voir et senza mentir - Que cist chastiaus [Mongibel] si est feez; - Sachiez que ço est veritez: - Nus hons ne puet caienz mori»].

Are we getting any nearer to our fifteenth-century Apennine Sibyl, a sorcerer whose abode lies in a magical cave set beneath an Italian mountain, in which unending sensual joys are offered to brave, unsuspecting knights?

Maybe. However, the progression towards an Apennine Sibyl is not in the least over. A further step is still to be taken toward a sensual, lecherous enchanter. That's what will happen in a French literary environment, with a transfer and an adaptation of the Matter of Britain to a different cultural milieu.

We are about to behold a further transformation of Morgan le Fay, as she appears in the romance *Lestoire de Merlin*: a seductive necromancer, a dark lady whose ensnaring fascination can well lure a knight into sin. As we will see in the next article.

16. Morgan, an inviting, ardent sorcerer

Bit by bit, step by step we are venturing into a most flimsy but wholly substantial trail, which is leading our enquiry from Morgan le Fay, an antique character belonging to the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle, to the Apennine Sibyl, living beneath a mountain which raises its cliff in the Italian Apennines.

We have started from Morgan le Fay and her original description as a benign healer and oracle, soon turning into an experienced necromancer and an evil fay in close contact with the powers of the Netherworld, and connected to a mountain and to some sort of realm of joys. In the medieval works in which references to that are found, Morgan's mountain does not appear to be set in the Italian Apennines.

We are now about to witness the next phase in her transformation. And we will do it by opening the vellum leaves of a precious illuminated manuscript (Additional MS 10292) preserved at the British Library in London, which contains, among many fine miniatures, a beautiful image which portrays young Arthur in the very moment he draws the magical kingly sword from the stone.

Fig. 55 - Young Arthur removes the sword from the stone (*Lestoire de Merlin*, manuscript Additional MS 10292, British Library, folium 99r)

The manuscript, dating to 1316, bears testimony to the great diffusion of the Matter of Britain among French-speaking readers, with what scholars calls the 'Lancelot-Grail' or the 'Vulgata Cycle', an elaboration process that had already started in the early thirteenth century.

The manuscript contains *Lestoire de Merlin* (*The History of Merlin*) and in it a new astounding description of Morgan le Fay is set down. At Folium 152r, we find again the Morgan we already know, a skilled necromancer and savant:

«[...] Morgan, who had been a clever student with Merlin [...] many wonders she learned from him about astronomy and necromancy and she gained a wide knowledge of them» (in the original Old French text: «[...] Morgain de merlin qui moult estoit boine clergesse [...] maintes merveilles li aprinst dastrenomie et dingremance et ele les detint moult bien»).

Fig. 56 - Morgan as a skilled magician from *Lestoire de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 10292, British Library, folium 152r)

But then, at Folium 177r, this description takes an utterly different hue. At the beginning, the author insists on the great proficiency acquired by Morgan in all arts:

«she was a most talented scholar - and she had a deep knowledge of astronomy because Merlin had taught her - [...] and she had learned so much that she was called, by the people in her own country and throughout

the world, Morgan the Fay, King Arthur's sister, owing to the wonders she achieved across the country»

[In the original Old French text: «si estoit a merveilles boine cleriesse - et dastrenomie savoit ele asses car merlins len avoit aprinse - [...] et tant aprinst qui puis fu ele des gens del pais et de la terre appelee morgain la fee la seror le roy artu por les merveilles que ele fist puis el pais»].

Fig. 57 - Another excerpt on Morgan from *Lestoire de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 10292, British Library, folium 177r)

Finally, the most striking words are written:

«This Morgan was a young damsel and very cheerful and lively - but she was dark in her face, her flesh round without being too skinny nor too plump - but she was very inviting and attractive in her body, and her limbs were so wonderfully well-shaped and lissome and graceful - But she was the most ardent woman in all Britain, and the most lecherous».

[In the original Old French text: «Icele morgain iert iouene damoisele et gaie durement et moult enuoisie - mais moult estoit brune de vis et dune roonde charneure ne trop maigre ne trop cras - mais moult estoit aperte et avenans de cors et de menmbres si estoit droite et plisans a merveilles et bien chantans - Mais ele estoit la plus chaude feme de toute la grant bertaigne et la plus luxurieuse»].

Fig. 58 - Morgan's sensual traits as they appear in *Lestoire de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 10292, British Library, folium 177r)

Here we are: another step in the transformation of Morgan le Fay into something else has now been performed, with the appearance of an unchaste, lascivious sinner who, in the lines that follow, beguiles the knight Guyomar and has an encounter with him.

And this new voluptuous trait of Morgan will never leave Arthur's sister. For instance, we also find it in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, another French romance which is part of the 'Vulgata Cycle'. Let's read the following excerpt taken from British Library's manuscript Add. MS 10293 (Folium 169v), written in the early fourteenth century:

«She was unworthy and ardent with lust» (in the Old French text: «Elle fu laide et chaude de luxure»).

Fig. 59 - Morgan as an lecherous sorcerer in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folium 169v)

With *Lestoire de Merlin* and *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, Morgan le Fay has taken on an additional trait which draws her nearer to the prophetess and evil sorcerer we know from Andrea da Barberino's romance *Guerrino the Wretch* (Fig. 6):

«the handsomest woman his eyes had never beheld; [...] she is Dame Sibyl [...] She had in herself all beauty and honesty; her limbs were of perfect gracefulness and of larger size than in common women, and she was of so attractive a colour that he was nearly deflected from his firm resolution [...] she showed him her own beauty and her white flesh and her breasts which looked like polished ivory».

[In the original Italian text: «una bella donna piu che li ochii soi mai havesse veduto; [...] quella e madona la Sibilla [...] Era in lei tuta belleza et honesta; li membri soi era de smesurata zentileza de grandezza piu che comuneuale e tanta colorita che quasi del suo proposito el cauo [...] mostrandoli la sua belleza e le sue bianche carne e le mamelle che pareano proprio che fosseno da volio»].

zionfeno a uno grande zardino a una bellissima roza tua
qui erano piu de cinquanta damifelle l'una bella: e l'altra piu: Tute se re/
uolfeno uerfo de lui. & in mezo de quele era una bella donna piu che li
ochii foi mai haueffe ueduto: et una de quefte tre li diffe quella e madoa

la Sibilla et in uerfo lei andono et lei ueniua i uerfo loro: & zionto apre
fo lei fe inzinchio Guerino: e lei fe inchino e prefelo per la mano & diffe
ben uegna mefere Guerino: & lui la faluto dicendo. Quella uirtu in la

fforzaua farli piu belli fembianti. E tanto era la fua uageza che ogni cor/
po humano hauerca inganato: & cum dolci folazi e cū bella recoglieza.
Era in lei tuta belleza & honefta: li membri foi era de fme furata zentileza
de grandezza piu che comuneuale e tanta colorita che quafi del fuo propo
fito el cauo. Lui era fmarito fra molti rofari pieni de fpinte: fe dio per fua

ma non per pigri non per iudice in per promere non uone ma pa
lezare cui fosse el fuo padre. La fera fo menato in una richa camera: e la Si-
billa uene con tuti quelli piacerie ziochi che fosse possibile che a uno corpo
humano fe potesse fare per farlo innamorare: e quando lui fu collegato in lo
lecto lei fe li zito da lato mostrandoli la fua belleza e le fue bianche carne e le
mamelles che pareano proprio che foffeno da uolio: et lo Melchino de capo
fu preso de lo ardente amore. E fatose lo segno de la fanta croce per questo

Fig. 60 - A selection of excerpts from *Guerrino the Wretch* in which a most sensual Sibyl is portrayed (from Chapters CXLV and CXLVII of the edition printed in 1480 in Venice)

However, this gradual transformation process is not yet over. In the next article, we will witness to another mutation in the distinguishing aspects of Morgan le Fay. This time, it will be a new inclination shown by the fairy for the confinement of brave knights in enchanted prisons: a tendency that the Apennine Sibyl will share as well. As we will see in the next article.

17. Many knights imprisoned by different fays

It truly appears that the literary character of Morgan le Fay, King Arthur's half-sister in the poems and romances belonging to the Matter of Britain, has undergone a transformation process across the twelfth, thirteenth and fourteenth centuries, as all scholars have already recorded in a vast number of research papers.

The interesting aspect is that the evolutionary path achieved by Morgan seems to head unswervingly towards a figure that is not so different from

the Apennine Sibyl we already know, a character who popped up almost from nothing at the beginning of the fifteenth century.

Are we treading the right road? Maybe yes, because we just need to follow the succeeding steps in Morgan's transformation to retrieve further astounding findings.

Let's open again the vellum leaves of *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, as taken from the illuminated manuscript Add. MS 10293 preserved at the British Library in London, dating to the early fourteenth century. At Folium 167r we strike upon another remarkable peculiarity, specifically referred to Morgan le Fay.

Because Morgan, in grief and wrath after an unsuccessful love affair, has cast a spell over a valley, which is turned into an enchanted prison for knights:

«a valley [...] from which no knight nor friends of him can leave once they have entered it - if they hold in their soul a love which is untrue [...] The valley was full of knights and was encircled by the air - And as soon as a knight entered it - he could not leave it - he was not allowed to leave because he was a knight [...] So it was that valley - the people of the country called it the Valley of No Return - and others called it the Valley of Untrue Lovers».

[In the original Old French text: «vn val [...] que iamais a nul ior nen isteroit sez amis ne chevaliers qui y entrast aussi - portant quil eust vers amors fausse [...] Li vals estoit tous plains de chevaliers et estoit tous enclos del air - Et si tost com vns chevaliers y entrast - ia puis issuee ne entree ni veist - ne nen peust issir pourcoi il fust chevaliers [...] En tel maniere estoient el val - si lapeloient cil del pais le val sans retor - Et li autre le val des faus amans»].

So it is apparent that Morgan le Fay shares another remarkable trait with the Sibyl of the Apennines: they both have a penchant for confining knights in some kind of restricted area bounded by witchcraft, the Sibyl's cave for the latter and the Valley of No Return for the former.

Fig. 61 - Morgan's Valley of No Return from *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folia 167r and 167v)

However, the Sibyl's cave was a land of eternal joy, provided with all sort of riches and food, and gladdened by the presence of sensual, beautiful damsels. And what about the Valley of No Return? Let's read what the manuscript reports:

Fig. 62 - Enjoying life at Morgan's Valley of No Return from *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folium 167v)

«And some of the knights had with them their lovers, and their squires who from their estates brought to them their goods and clothes and birds and food - So they had all a man's heart may wish for - and there also were many nice abodes [...]»

[In the original Old French text: «Et de tels y auoit qui y orent lor amies par amors avec euls et lor ualles qui de lor terres lor apportoient lor apportoient lor relies et lor reubes et lor oisiaus et qui lor atornoient lor viandes - Et neporquant il auoient quant que a cors domme puet appartenir - et moult y auoit de beles mesons [...]».

A similar tale is told in *Le Livre d'Artus*, another romance belonging to the 'Vulgata Cycle' (Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, Français 337). Morgan le Fay, turned down by Queen Guinevere following an inappropriate love affair, flees to the forest of Sarpenic and, by the power of her magic, «had that the most beautiful abode in the world built for her convenience» (in the original Old French text: «fist faire sales por ester les plus beles du monde»). There, she set up her confinement place (Folia 187v and 188r):

«Morgan cast her spell [...] with such a might that all the knights and all the dames who acted insincerely in their love affairs [...] be never allowed to leave once they had entered».

[In the original Old French text: «si gita Morganz son enchantement [...] qui ot tel force que tuit li chevalier et toutes les dames qui eussent fausse en lor amors [...] sil i entrassent iamet ne sen issent»].

Fig. 63 - Morgan's enchanted confinement place for knights from *Le Livre d'Artus* (manuscript Français 337, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Département des Manuscrits, folia 187v and 188r)

Sure there are many differences between the two confinement places, Morgan's and the Sibyl's, as the Valley of No Return allows squires to come and go from the site, which only confines knights, and the Valley also contains chapels to attend the religious service: two features that are not available at the Sibyl's cave.

However, the overall impression is that a same type of magical place is devoted to the confinement of knights: each person of that rank, once entered, «is forced to stay there» («il y est remes a force» in the *Lancelot*). Both places are ruled by a similar evil queen. And both places, though a product of witchcraft, offer some sort of blissful life, a reminiscence of antique Avalon, Morgan's enchanted island.

Fig. 64 - Knights are forced to stay in Morgan's Valley of No Return from *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folium 168r)

Morgan le Fay and the Apennine Sibyl. Two figures who seem to get closer and closer to each other as centuries unfold.

Just an insubstantial illusion? Just a chimerical fancy?

Not in the least. Because, as we will see in the next article, the character of Morgan will begin to actually merge with that of a Sibyl. And it won't be only a matter of merging traits and features, as we already saw.

It will be a matter of far more solidity. It will be a matter of names.

18. Morgan, Sebile and a wretched knight

With this series of articles, we are trying to unveil the true essence of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl. To this purpose we are seeking to remove the many literary additions that have been conferred to the sibilline myth throughout the centuries.

Our guess is that the character of a Sibyl of the Apennine was basically taken from a much more antique profile: Morgan le Fay, a primary figure belonging to the Arthurian cycle.

What can we say up to now? What sort of results has our search achieved so far? Let's try to summarize our preliminary findings.

Following our initial finding that no Apennine Sibyl is ever mentioned in antiquity, and considering a number of narrative episodes contained in earlier chivalric works which seem to portray a number of situations we already encountered in the Apennine Sibyl's literature, with Morgan the Fay appearing in a similar role at least in one instance (*Floriant et Florète*) and under an Italian mountain (a Sicilian volcano), we have started from the same Morgan and her original description as a benign healer and oracle, soon taking a decisive twist towards the portrait of an experienced necromancer and evil fay in close contact with the powers of the Netherworld, with a specific parallelism established with classical Sibyls as stated by Hartmann von Aue in his *Erec*. Moreover, Morgan began to be connected to a mountain and some sort of realm of joys. In addition to that, she started to be depicted as a lecherous woman, actually the most lecherous in the whole Britain. Finally, she liked to hold knights in an enchanted place of confinement, where they enjoyed their time by living a blissful life.

On the other side, we know that the Apennine Sibyl was an experienced necromancer and an evil fay, who lived in a subterranean realm, buried beneath a mountain. She was a lascivious being, and she enjoyed to hold

the visiting knight as prisoners in her hidden abode, absorbed in an endless life of sensual joys.

Is that enough to say that the idea of an Apennine Sibyl was possibly inspired by Morgan le Fay?

Can all that be just trivial coincidences? Just mere chance? Just obvious correspondences that may possibly happen, with some sort of frequency, in a same chivalric literary setting?

The answer is certainly no. This is no coincidence.

There is a strict connection between Morgan and Sibyls. And this connection is stated once more - after having already been declared by Hartmann von Aue in his *Erec* dating to 1185 - in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, the French romance we already saw in previous articles, which dates to the early fourteenth century and possibly even earlier.

Let's fly again through the leaves of manuscript Add. 10293 preserved at the British Library in London. At Folium 281v we find a truly amazing episode, that of a sleeping Lancelot, caught in the forest in such defenseless state by three fairies. Three fairies, of whom one is Morgan, and a second one bears a name that is not the product of chance:

Fig. 65 - The excerpt on Morgan, the Queen of Soresan and Sebile from *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folium 281v)

«While Lancelot was sleeping [...] a Queen who reigned over the land of Sorestan passed by [...] And she saw Lancelot's horse grazing the grass [...] So she called for two dames [of her retinue] of which the first was Morgan le Fay - and the other Sebile - And the two were the most skilled women in the world as to enchantments, apart from the Lady of the Lake».

[In the original Old French text: «quantancelot fu remes dormant [...] par illuec passa une Royme qui estoit raine de la terre de sornestan [...] Et elle regarda le chevalancelot qui paissoit de lerbe [...] Si apela ii dames dont li vne auoit anon Morgue la fee - et l'autre sebile - Et ce estoient les ii femmes del monde qui plus sauoient denchantemens sans la dame del lac»].

Who do we find here as a member of a most distinguished company, including a queen and our well-known Morgan le Fay? We find nothing less but «Sebile», the Old French world for 'Sibyl'. And we are also told that Morgan and Sibyl are the greatest wizards in the whole world, beside the Lady of the Lake (another character playing an important role in the Matter of Britain, to her belongs the arm handing the sword Excalibur over to King Arthur out of the the waters of an enchanted lake). A supreme magical power that we saw had been already acknowledged by Hartmann von Aue, who had expressed a similar comparison in his poem *Erec*.

Fig. 66 - The name and character «Sebile» as it appears in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folium 281v)

Once more, Morgan and Sibyl - also appearing in other *Lancelot's* manuscripts as «Sebille» or «Sibile», as H. Oskar Sommer reports - show their close relationship: now they start travelling together, with a Sibyl embodied in a brand new literary character, a witchess that sounds as a sort of alternative identity of Morgan herself, being endowed with comparable powers.

What do the two ladies do with poor sleeping Lancelot? If you remember, they both seem to share a common tendency for detaining brave knights in confinement. So they fetch Lancelot to their castle and awake him. However, they fail to recognise him, and he does not tell them his own name.

Now the Queen of Soresan, Morgan le Fay and Sebile, in their most charming attire, ask the bewildered knight to pick his choice: which one of the three will he elect as his lover? However, he refuses to choose, a great offence to the three sensual ladies (who are portrayed together in a charming miniature at Folium 281v).

Fig. 67 - The miniature which portrays Morgan, the Queen of Soresan and Sebile from *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folium 281v)

Subsequently, when a damsel, who is in charge to look after him in the prison, asks him for his name, he sadly unveils his own identity, that of an unfortunate knight who lost his father, inheritance and rank:

«My name is Lancelot of the Lake, the Wretch».

[In the original Old French text: «iou ai a non lancelot del lac li mescheans»].

Fig. 68 - Lancelot unveils his name and wretched condition to a damsel in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folium 282r)

So we have a Sibyl and a wretched knight: Lancelot of the Lake.

The perfume of the right trail is now becoming stronger and stronger, if we just think of the Apennine Sibyl and the knight hero who meets her in Andrea da Barberino's fifteenth-century romance: *Guerrino*, also known as the «Meschino».

«Meschino»: the Italian word which exactly matches the Old French word «mescheans», or 'wretch'.

Morgan and the Apennine Sibyl are now almost touching by the tips of their magical, literary fingers. An amazing encounter which seems to take place after the crossing by the two enchantress of a mythical bridge spanning over an abyss of centuries.

19. Morgan and Sebile join the same party

In our previous articles, we have pointed at the many literary additions that appear to have been conferred to the Apennine Sibyl's legend, in the form of episodes, narratives and situations which are present in Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* and Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, and whose origin can be retrieved in earlier chivalric

romances, written in the Middle Ages. Then we have followed the footsteps of Morgan le Fay, whose attributes have been changing across the centuries, until she has gradually turned into something which is remarkably close to the figure of a Sibyl of the Apennines. We have also seen that Morgan and classical Sibyls are actually tightly connected, starting from Hartmann von Aue's *Erec* and passing through *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, in which a character called «Sebile» is portrayed as a close intimate of Morgan, and a most powerful wizard.

This Sebile is also described elsewhere as a true friend of Morgan and other mighty fairies. Let's look at the tale narrated in the ancient work *Prophécies de Merlin* (*The Prophecies of Merlin*), according to scholars originally written around 1275 possibly in Italy, in Venice. Of this we have a beautiful specimen contained in British Library's manuscript Additional 25434, dating to the early fourteenth century.

In this narrative, we find an amusing episode concerning Sebile, Morgan, a Queen of Norgales and a dame of Avalon (who is treated here as a different character from Morgan). All of them are skilled sorceresses, and Sebile is openly defined as “the enchantress”.

Fig. 69 - The passage on «Sebile l'enchanterresse» from the *Prophécies de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 25434, British Library, folium 173r)

This excerpt stages a funny magical fight between the dame of Avalon on one side and the three other fays on the other, in two subsequent steps. But the dame from Avalon is much more powerful, and by using her enchanted rings she repels all spells cast by Sebile, the Queen of Norgales and then Morgan, leaving them «wholly naked and in full embarrassment» («furent toutes nues et eles erent honte» in Old French).

Fig. 70 - The Queen of Norgales and Sebile defeated by the dame of Avalon from the *Prophécies de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 25434, British Library, folium 174v)

However, Sebile and the others were great friends, and the episode ends up with the dame of Avalon who embraces the other fays dearly («lors li giete la dame davalon les bras au col» in Old French):

«The dame of Avalon had great joy and much fun, and the same joy had the Queen of Norgales and Sebile the Enchantress».

[In the original Old French text: «Agrant ioie et agrant fete eu la dame davalon et mout fust grande ioie de la reyne de norgales et de sebile lenchanterresse»].

Fig. 71 - Sebile the Enchantress shares a same feeling of joy with the dame of Avalon from the *Prophécies de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 25434, British Library, folium 174v)

Once more, we see an ancient literary source which states that Morgan le Fay and Sebile the Enchantress were close friends. And both of them were mighty witches. The two characters knew each other and appeared together on stage, sharing the same narrative and the same magical episodes. And the whole narrative seems to have been written in Venice: this means that more than a century before the appearance of an Apennine Sibyl, Italian scribes already knew well about the close relationship which existed between Morgan and Sebile.

And the time comes when that close intimate of Morgan straightly replaces Morgan herself in her role as ruler of a magical castle: it will actually be the Sibyl, «Sebile», the dame we stumble upon after we have crossed the enchanted gates and enter the bewitched abode.

This is exactly what happens in *Huon of Bordeaux*, the epic poem dating to the thirteenth century which we already encountered in a previous article. And this happens just beyond the metal scourges ceaselessly lashing and whipping (an instance of magical gates that Antoine de la Sale will subsequently refer to in his account of a visit to the Sibyl's cave):

«The son of Sewin [Huon] from the town of Bordeaux, stroke three great blows on the golden basin [which stood beside the bronze guards]. A maiden in the castle listened to the resounding noise, her name was Sebile, a most handsome lady» (in the original French text: «Li fieus Sewins, de Bordiax la cité, Sour le bacin qui fu f'or esmeré a fru trois cos par moult grande fierté. Une pucele ou u palais listé, Sebile ot nom, moult par ot de biauté»).

And there are also occurrences in which this «Sebile» reappears on Morgan's side, in the same fairy setting depicting an enchanted place connected to some sort of mountain. All this happens in *La Chanson d'Esclarmonde*, a poem which narrates further deeds of Huon of Bordeaux, and whose text can be read in manuscript L.II.14, preserved at the National University Library in Turin (folia 354v-374r), dated by scholars to year 1311. In this article, we will follow the transcript published by Max Schweigel in 1889.

Knight Huon and his lover Esclarmonde are brought to the magical land of Monmur, where King Auberon reigns (a character that will appear in

Shakespeare's *Midsummer Night's Dream* as 'Oberon'). There, they are welcomed by a distinguished party of fairy ladies:

«In Monmur [...] The four dames [...] - Dame Oriande, dame Marse, Sibyl and Morgan - who is so good - and made so astounding enchantments» (in the original French text: «a Monmur [...] Les IV dames [...] - Dame Oriande dame Marse i sera Sebile et Morgue - qui tant de bonté a - et nostres sires tel miracle i moustra»).

Fig. 72 - Sebile and Morgan together in the *Chanson d'Esclarmonde* (manuscript L.II.14, National University Library in Turin, from verse 3205 as transcribed in *Esclarmonde, Clarisse et Florent, Yde et Olive: Drei Fortsetzungen der Chanson von Huon de Bordeaux, nach der einzigen Turiner Handschrift zum erstmalig veröffentlicht* by Max Schweigel, Marburg, 1889)

Thus, Sebile is now fully enrolled as Morgan's fairy mate, in a magical place which is a house of joy and eternal youth. A place, Monmur, which is located beneath a mountain:

«Each of the ladies goes to Esclarmonde - Dame Oriande takes her by the hand - and dame Morgan by the other hand [...] - Dame Sibyl helps her to stand up [...] - To the Garden of Eden - To the fountain of youth that is there - they went there as soon as they thought of it - Under the mountain everybody has his own pleasure - The four dames all took her - and threw Esclarmonde in the fountain - Thrice they threw her in it - And she became

handsome and had no more pain at all - when she went out from the fountain she was young - she will be thirty years old - until the end of the world».

[In the original French text: «A Esclarmonde cascune deles va - Dame Oriande par la main prise la - et dame Morgue par lautre le gbra [...] - Dame Sebile au leuer li aida [...] - En paradis terrestre par dela - A la fontaine de Jouent quil i a - tantost i furent ele devisa - Sus la montaigne cascune joie a - Les IV dames cascune prise la - En la fontaine Esclarmonde bouta - Et par III fois cascune le bouta - Adont fu bele ne nule dolour na - Si jou(e)ne fu quant on len resaca - a XXX ans deage ou pint sera - Dusque adont que li mons finera»].

A Esclarmonde cascune deles va
Dame Oriande par la main prise la
& dame Morgue par lautre le gbra
& dame Marse par les flans laccola
Dame Sebile au leuer li aida
Quant fu en hair ca terre ne toca
Dame Oriande maïtenāt soushaida
E Dix dist ele qui toute riens creas
Entre n^o V nous soushaiderai ja
En paradis terrestre par dela
A la fontaine de Jouent quil i a
Tantost i furent 9 ele devisa
Sus la montaigne cascune se troua
A la fontaine dont cascune joie a
Morgue la fée la dame despoulla
Les IV dames cascune prise la
En la fontaine Esclarmode bouta
& par III fois cascune le bouta
Adont fu bele ne nule dolour na
Si jou(e)ne fu quant on len resaca
9 a XXX ans deage ou point sera
Dusques adont que li mons finera

Fig. 73 - The magical mountain mentioned in the *Chanson d'Esclarmonde* (manuscript L.II.14, National University Library in Turin, from verse 3318 as transcribed in *Esclarmonde, Clarisse et Florent, Yde et Olive: Drei Fortsetzungen der Chanson von Huon de Bordeaux, nach der einzigen Turiner Handschrift zum erstenmal veröffentlicht* by Max Schweigel, Marburg, 1889)

And another magical mountain is mentioned, one we already know:

«Great was the joy they felt - But that joy did not last for long - Because King Arthur was to leave for Mount Etna» (in the original French text:

«Grans fu la joie que on i demena - Mais cele joie out petit lor dura - Car rois Artus a Mongibel sen va»).

Grans fu la joie que on i demena
Mais cele joie mout petit lor dura
Car rois Artus a Mōgibel sen va

Fig. 74 - The Mongibel (Mount Etna in Italy) referred to in the *Chanson d'Esclarmonde* (manuscript L.II.14, National University Library in Turin, from verse 3456 as transcribed in *Esclarmonde, Clarisse et Florent, Yde et Olive: Drei Fortsetzungen der Chanson von Huon de Bordeaux, nach der einzigen Turiner Handschrift zum erstenmal veröffentlicht* by Max Schweigel, Marburg, 1889)

So a golden thread unwinding across the centuries connects Morgan to Sebile. The two figures seem to be so thoroughly intertwined that not only they are represented as companions, but they become almost interchangeable.

And in the fourteenth century, around a hundred years before *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* were written, both fays, Morgan and Sebile, appear to be connected to an enchanted mountain, in which eternal youth and pleasures can be experienced.

Are we getting closer to our Apennine Sibyl? Of course we are. And we are going to make a further step ahead in the next article.

20. King Arthur's eternal life with the Sibyl (instead of Morgan)

Sibyl and Morgan, Morgan and Sibyl. As centuries go by, the two mythical figures seem to increasingly mix up, as if they should eventually converge into one single literary character.

We have another amazing proof of such process of gradual combination, a proof which comes to us from the very core of the Arthurian cycle: the myth concerning the ever-continuing life of King Arthur, who according to the legend would still be living an immortal life in the enchanted island of Avalon, attended by his half-sister Morgan, until the day comes for him to come back as a ruling king again.

In a previous article, we already saw that this legend underwent a most remarkable relocation from Avalon to an Italian mountain and volcano, Mount Etna, as it is narrated in *Floriant et Florète*, a chivalric poem dating to the second half of the thirteenth century, with Morgan transplanted right into the land of Italy: a highly significant clue which clearly indicates that Morgan le Fay and the Apennine Sibyl are much closer than we might think.

In addition to that, we are also able to retrieve another striking hint: it comes from the *Wartburgkrieg*, a most illustrious piece of German medieval literature, which recounts a legendary poetical contest that would have been held at the Castle of Wartburg, in Thüringen, in the year 1207.

Of this contest, providing precious information to scholars about poetry sung by German minstrels during the Middle Ages, we have an exquisite account in the *Jenaer Liederhandschrift*, a fourteenth-century manuscript (Ms. El. f. 101) preserved at the Thüringer Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek in Jena, Germany.

And the manuscript, at Folium 135r, which features the poetical confrontation between minstrels Wolfram von Eschenbach and Klingsor of Hungary, makes a direct, significant, unexpected reference to King Arthur and his resting place. However, this is neither Avalon nor Morgan's.

There is a mountain, instead. And a Sibyl (Fig. 1 and 2):

«Felicia, the Sibyl's child,
and Juno, who are with Arthur in the mountain,
have flesh and bones like us.
[...] They still live in vigour [...]
Arthur lives in the mountain as a hero [...]
The Sibyl's child, Felicia,
and Juno are both with Arthur there».

[In the Old German text: «Felicia, sibillen kint,
Unde iuno, die mit arthus in dem berge synt,
Die habent vleisch sam wir unde ouch gebeyne.
[...] sie lebent noch in vrece [...]
Wie arthus in dem berge lebe und ouch der helde mere [...]

Sybillen kynt felicia
 Unde iuno, die synt beyde myr arthuse da»].

Fig. 75 - King Arthur living an eternal life beneath a mountain with a Sibyl from the *Wartburgkrieg* (manuscript El. f. 101 *Jenaer Liederhandschrift*, Thüringer Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek in Jena, Germany, folium 135r)

Once more, Morgan le Fay and a Sibyl appear to entwine their legendary roles. In the *Wartburgkrieg*, a Sibyl takes altogether the place of Morgan in her primary position as Arthur's healer and companion of his neverending life in Avalon.

And Avalon itself becomes a mountain. Just like in *Florian et Florète*, in which Avalon was turned into Mount Etna.

It truly appears that a Sibyl, whose role as an enchantress of equal might as Morgan's had already been stated by German poet Hartmann von Aue, is also fully authorised to take on the very garments of King Arthur's half-sister and play Morgan's narrative tasks as a genuine, almost original

literary character belonging to the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian Cycle.

Fig. 76 - King Arthur and a Sibyl from the *Wartburgkrieg* (manuscript El. f. 101 *Jenaer Liederhandschrift*, Thüringer Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek in Jena, Germany, folium 135r)

Time is coming for the birth of an Apennine Sibyl, who is to inherit many of the traits that are typically associated with Morgan le Fay, with an enchanted abode to be set beneath a remote mountain in Italy.

However, there is still place to carry on with our quest, so as to find additional instances of such close kinship between our two legendary ladies. Because there are more of them: further clues that we are not on the wrong route. As we will see in the next article.

21. Morgan and the Sibyl in a mirror

We are now about to reach more recent centuries. We are leaving the High Middle Ages and are now entering a later medieval period, getting closer and closer to that early fifteenth century when the radiance of our Apennine Sibyl began to shine with all its potency.

We are getting to the middle of the fourteenth century, a period in which the lore concerning Morgan le Fay has already made its way through time, featuring a remarkable tendency to intertwine and combine with legends and stories that narrated of fairy Sibyls, depicted as associated with Arthur's sister herself.

However, the Apennine Sibyl has not yet appeared, and the character of Morgan is still strong; yet she is markedly taking on many of the traits that will be specific to the Sibyl of Norcia.

Let's consider a highly interesting work, *Ly Myreur des Histors* (*The Mirror of Tales*), written by Jean des Preis d'Outremeuse, an author from Liège, in the early second half of the fourteenth century. His chronicle, made up by four books, is a sort of history of the world which starts from the mythical Flood and ends up with the years the author was living. Manuscripts of it exist at the Bibliothèque Royale de Belgique in Bruxelles (no. 10455-10462 and others) (Fig. 1). In this article, we will follow the transcript published by Stanislas Bormans in 1877.

Fig. 77 - The first folium and first sentence of *Ly Myreur des Histors* (manuscript 10455, Bibliothèque royale de Belgique, Brussels, folium 1r)

It is in Book II (Volume IV of the transcript) that we find, again, Morgan le Fay («Morghe») and her enchanted island, Avalon. To the island, a knight arrives: his name is Ogier the Danish, he serves Charlemagne, and he is cast there following a shipwreck.

There is something on the island. It is Morgan's castle. A place for pleasure, a place for bliss. And she invites the knight to enter her abode:

«I came to ask you to come and stay at the Castle of Leisure. There you will not find any other man than Arthur, my brother [...] No men are there, but damsels».

[In the original Old French text: «je vous veng queirir por venir en castel Plaisant herbegier. Ilh n'y at nul homme que Artus, mon frere, [...] Ilh n'y at plus homme, fors que damoisellez»].

Fig. 78 - The excerpt on Morgan's «castel Plaisant» from *Ly Myreur des Histors* (as transcribed by Stanislas Bormans, Brussels, 1877, p. 51)

A castle of pleasures, full of damsels. A castle which is enchanted («li castel est i lis faieis»). A castle that is concealed to anybody, and cannot be seen if not by its inhabitants («castel Plaisant, qui astoit invisible à cascon fors à cheuz de laiens»). A castle of sorcery, made of air and illusions («et n'astoit que vens et fantomme»):

«And [Merlin] taught that knowledge to Morgan, King Arthur's sister, and to many other women in the Kingdom of Britain, by teaching them the antique wisdom, as to how to create an abode made of pure air in which to

live forever without growing old. Morgan knew that enchantment better than Merlin himself, and she made the Castle of Leisure where she inhabited; and there were many damsels»

[In the original Old French text: «Et [Merlin] aprist la science à Morghe, le serour le roy Artus, et à pluseurs autres femmes de la royalme de Bretangne, en enformant elles de la scienche perpetuee, à faire habitations pour demoreir à touz jours sens avilhier et de pure aire. Cheste faierie ensi par destinee Morghe en soit plus ancors que Merlin; et fist le castel Plaisant où ilh habitoit; et oit deleis li des pucieles asseis»].

monde à Merlin et à sa mere, et tant que Merlin en soit plus que nul altre; et si astoit vrais xristoiens et avoit fianche en Dieu et savoit tout; et de luy fut la scienche plus ensachie et appreee " que de nul devant. Et aprist la scienche à Morghe, le serour le roy Artus, et à pluseurs autres femmes de la royalme de Bretangne, en enformant elles de la scienche perpetuee, à faire habitations pour demoreir à touz jours sens avilhier ' et de pure aire. Cheste faierie ensi par destinee Morghe en soit plus ancors que Merlins; et fist le castel Plaisant où ilh habitoit; et oit deleis li des pucieles asseis, et oit IIII hommez tant sorlement : Artus, Gawain, Ogier et Alberon, qui fut li fis Morghe, del roy Meliadus de Lonnois, qui fut peire del

Fig. 79 - The excerpt on Morgan's ability to magically set up enchanted abodes from *Ly Myreur des Histors* (as transcribed by by Stanislas Bormans, Brussels, 1877, p. 53 and 54)

Morgan's castle is starting to look like the cave of the Apennine Sibyl, as it will be portrayed some fifty years later by Andrea da Barberino in his *Guerrino the Wretch*.

And the similarities are not over. The castle and the cave share a same lavish richness:

«there are the most charming gardens in it, and trees bearing all kinds of perfumed fruits. And the castle was made of fine rubies, emeralds, sapphires, diamonds, beryllium and all precious stones; [...] all tables are made of pure gold, the beds of chalcedony and sapphire...».

[In the original Old French text: «jardins y at mult dilicieux, et toute altour arbres de toutez manerez de fruitez, qui getent grant odour. Et fut li casteais fais de fins rubis, esmeraide, saphier, dyamans, et de jacinte, de perilh, et de toutez pires precieuses; [...] les tablez sont trestout de fin or; les lithier de calcidoine et de saphir...»].

» mon castel. » — « Damme, dist-ilh, de moy faitez mon gré ¹. » Adont vinrent vers le castel, qui pais n'astoit de pirez, de calheauz, de bois, de terre manovreis, mains si fait que vous oreis. Ilh astoit tres grans et tres fort; IIII tours at et I dongnon; les asemenchez ² at defors et dedens toutez doblez; trois viviers qui encloient entour; jardins y at mult dilicieux, et toute altour arbres de toutez manerez de fruitez, qui getent grant odour. Et fut li casteais fais de fins rubis, esmeraide, saphier, dyamans, et de jacinte ³, de perilh ⁴ et de toutez pires precieuses. Deseurs les viviers at trois pons, tout de berilh cristal, entrelachiez d'yvoir; les scampnez ⁵ sont de jaspe, vers et roge; les tablez sont trestout de fin or; les leithier ⁶ de calcidoine ⁷ et de saphir; et les cuches sont de veleweal ⁸, les ⁹ de pelicans

Fig. 80 - The excerpt on Morgan's enchanted castle from *Ly Myreur des Histors* (as transcribed by by Stanislas Bormans, Brussels, 1877, p. 52)

And yet, Morgan's castle is a castle of pleasures («castel Plaisant»), and we know from the tale of the Apennine Sibyl that there is one specific way to offer true pleasure to brave knights:

«Ladies and damsels stayed there, tempting and desirable, without committing any sins; yet there was plenty of lust, and they liked to receive courtly cares».

[In the original Old French text: «Dammes et puciellez astoient là desduisantez sens pechiez faire; luxure heent mult, et sont desirantes cortoisie»].

Finally, as in the deepest bowels of the Sibyl's cave, nobody ever grew old, lost in neverending pleasures and oblivious of the outer world:

«Here I [Morgan] will inhabit until the Last Judgment [...] and each day we will live as if we were thirty years old [...] There Ogier lived for a longtime [...] every day in bliss and peace and holiness, as if he was twenty years old; and after eight days, he could not know who he was anymore, and all he forgot of the world».

[In the original Old French text: «Chiens demoreis jusqu'al jour de jugement [...] et toudis haitiez en eage de XXX ans [...] Là est Ogier demoreit lonc terme [...]; et est toudis en joie, pais et sancteit; [...] et quide XX ains avoir; passeit VIII jours, ihl ne seit là ilh est, ilh at tout oblieit le monde»].

de XXX ans. Atant entrent en castel où chis oiseais chantoient cascon sa canchon mult melodieusement. Dammes et pucielles estoient là desduisantez⁶ sens pechiez faire; luxure heent mult, et sont desirantes cortoisie; et li alcons se sont recordans⁷ qu'ilh ament mult le pechiet de luxure et

Fig. 81 - The excerpt on Morgan's enchanted castle from *Ly Myreur des Histors* (as transcribed by Stanislas Bormans, Brussels, 1877, p. 56)

la beateit; et dist Ogier : « A cuy est la maison? » Et Morghe dist : « Ilh » est à moy, s'en sereis sire à vous comment. Chiens demoreis jusqu'al » jour de jugement, que ne sereis perdans I cheval⁴, et toudis haitiez⁵ » en eage de XXX ans. » Atant li donne une anelet d'or : « Teneis, dist-

» ne pot mangier plus personnez. » Là est Ogier demoreit lonc terme, jusqu'à tant qu'ilh revient en Franche par necessiteit; et est toudis en joie, pais et sancteit; et at tout plains ses dois de aneais d'or à pires precieuses, et quide XX ains avoir; passeit VIII jours, ilh ne seit là ilh est, ilh at tout oblieit le monde.

Fig. 82 - The excerpt on Morgan's enchanted castle from *Ly Myreur des Histors* (as transcribed by Stanislas Bormans, Brussels, 1877, p. 56 and 58)

Here is Morgan's castle. A place of eternal joy and richness and enchantment. Only fifty years divide this abode of pleasure from the still-to-come cavern of the Apennine Sibyl.

And we also have another stunning example. A Sibyl, an invisible, enchanted place, a site where time seems to have its own magically slow speed. Is all that in the Apennines?

Not in the least. This story is set in Britain, before King Arthur's kingdom. If we read it, we cannot avoid thinking of our Sibyl of the Apennines, as we will see in the next article.

22. Sebille and her invisible castle (in ancient Britain)

«Two damsels came [to the two knights] and took them by their hands and escorted them to a charming room, in which they laid their weapons and dressed with new garments. After this they were brought to a large room where they found Sebille, the Dame of the Lake. When she saw them coming she welcomed them respectfully [...] Sirs, Sebille said, the tables are ready for the meal, please come and wash your hands, so she took them by their hands and they washed. She wanted to seat beside the King, with Floridas on the other side».

[In the original Old French text: «deux damoiselles furent illes appareillies qui les prindrent chacun par la main les menerent en une belle chambre ou ils se desarmerent et revesturent de nouveaux habiz. ce fait elles les menerent en la sale ou sebille la dame de leanc estoit Laquele quant elle les ver venir elle les receuyt honnourablement [...] Seigneurs dist sebille les tables sont mises pour le soup venez laver si les print par les mains et laverent. Elle fist seoir le roy puis elle au pres et Floridas au pres delle»].

Fig. 83 - Two brave knights visiting an enchanted castle ruled by «Sebille» from *Perceforest* (manuscript 3483, Bibliothèque de l'Arsenal, Paris, folia 116v and 117r)

Is that a passage taken from an Old French edition of Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch*? Is the large room buried beneath Mount Sibyl, in the Italian Apennines? Is that Sibyl («Sebille») the Apennine Sibyl?

It might well be so, as the above episode appears to be a copycat of a similar situation experienced by the knight Guerrino as he enters the Sibyl's cave for the first time.

However, we are in ancient Britain, and we are reading an excerpt drawn from *Perceforest*, a fourteenth-century chivalric romance, with no connection at all with the Apennines and the Apennine Sibyl.

Fig. 84 - The opening of the chivalric romance *Perceforest*, or *Premieres croniques de la Grant Bretagne que nous appellons a present Angleterre* (manuscript 3483, Bibliothèque de l'Arsenal, Paris, folium 10r)

Just a typical situation that is commonly retrieved in all chivalric romances? Yes indeed. But a few correspondences appear to be utterly striking. If we consider some of the sentences contained in Folium 114v and beyond in manuscript n. 3483 preserved at the Bibliothèque de

l'Arsenal in Paris, we find that many features which will be conferred to our Apennine Sibyl are also present in this work which narrates knightly stories set at a time when Arthur was not yet a king.

The two knights mentioned above are King Alexandre and knight Floridas. During their quest through Britain they stumble upon a very peculiar castle:

«They were told that they had got to the land of the Dame of the Lake. Where does she live, asked the King. Sir, one replied, her abode is just before your eyes [...] the squire said that [her castle] could not be seen [...] But the King said that on that land no castle nor manor was to be seen. Sir, by your mercy, there you will find a suitable place to house King Alexander. So the King said that he would gladly check it out. Sir, added the squire, the Dame of the Lake has arranged it by fairy enchantments so that it cannot be seen [...] Sure enough, said the King, you are telling me wonders. Sir, replied the squire to him, in the castle there are wonders which are even greater».

Fig. 85 - Sebille's enchanted castle from *Perceforest* (manuscript 3483, Bibliothèque de l'Arsenal, Paris, folium 114v)

[In the original Old French text: «nous sommes dirent ils a la dame du lac adont dist le roy ou demeure elle sire dist lun deulx elle demeure cy devant [...] dist le vallet on ne le puet veoir [...] dist le roy esse dedens terre il ny a dont ne chastel ne maison Sire sauls votre grace car il y a lieu et fust pour recevoir le roy alexandre Il me semble dist le roy quon le verroit. Sire dist le vallet la dame de leans la telement ordonne par fes enchantemens quon ne le puet veoir [...] Certes dist le roy tu me dis merveilles. En verite sire dist il elle y sont assez plus grandes»].

So the Dame of the Lake, whose name we will later find out to be «Sebille», is the master of an enchanted castle, which is concealed from man's sight. Just like a hidden realm set beneath a peak of the Apennines.

And what usually happens in this sort of place?

«Nobody could leave that forest because of the magical spells, as any person who had entered that place would never be able to depart».

[In the original Old French text: «ne pouvoit homme yssir des forests par les enchantemens et aussi nuls ny entroit qu en peust partir»].

Fig. 86 - Fairy enchantments cast over the surrounding forests from *Perceforest* (manuscript 3483, Bibliothèque de l'Arsenal, Paris, folium 115r)

So this Sebille presides over a kingdom which reminds us of a realm ruled by another Sibyl, the Apennine's. And time within the kingdom is marked by an odd behaviour, as the two knights find eventually out to their utter bewilderment, following their request to Sebille for one night's rest:

«When the Dame listened to the King's request, she decided to do according to her own will, as she actually did: because the King and

Floridas stayed at the castle for fifteen days, and thought they had been there for one single day only».

[In the original Old French text: «Quant la dame eut entendu le roy elle sapesa quelle en seroit autrement come elle fist car le roy et floridas y demourerent quinze iours et ny penserent davoit este que une nuit»].

Fig. 87 - Time speed at Sebille's enchanted castle from *Perceforest* (manuscript 3483, Bibliothèque de l'Arsenal, Paris, folium 115r)

But time is also a queer element within the Sibyl's cave in Italy, in which people stay forever young and are wholly forgetful of the outer world.

For the sake of completion, Sebille will be far most lucky than her Italian counterpart, the Apennine Sibyl: in *Perceforest*, she will succeed in seducing King Alexander, and King Arthur will be the product of her lineage.

According to scholars, *Perceforest* was written less than a hundred years before the literary appearance of the Apennine Sibyl.

Everything is now ready for the final transformation: the transplant of Morgan's legend into a lofty peak lost amid the Italian Apennines, in the form of her mate Sebille, or the Sibyl.

We are about to behold the birth of a Sibyl.

23. A recap and a momentous statement on the Sibyl of the Apennines

Time has come for us to recap the long journey we have made across many centuries in search of the medieval roots of our fifteenth-century Apennine Sibyl, and to summarise the main findings we have retrieved by perusing the many ancient manuscripts of the illustrious chivalric romances and poems of the Middle Ages.

We started our travel after having ascertained, in a previous paper (*The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*) that no reference to a Sibyl of the Apennines can be found in both medieval and Roman literature: no author, no romance, no chronicle, no ancient essay provides the least mention of a Sibyl who might have had her oracular site in the mountainous fastnesses of what we call today the Sibillini Mountain Range, set in the portion of the Apennines which runs through central Italy, between the provinces of Umbria and Marche.

Fig. 88 - The north-eastern side of the Sibillini Mountain Range, a portion of the Apennines set in central Italy

This is reason for which the Apennine Sibyl seems to have popped up from a puzzling void at the beginning of the fifteenth century: no hint of her presence is available before two fundamental works first mentioning her existence were written, Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* and Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

Having ascertained that, we have moved from a different starting point, by establishing a new assumption: the very nature of the Apennine Sibyl's legend appears to be veiled and removed from sight owing to a series of narrative additions and layers, which have been attached to the true essence of the sibilline myth in the Middle Ages, the centuries that precede that fifteenth century which saw the appearance of the Sibyl of the Apennines. We have to take all such disguising layers out if we want to behold and understand what the legend of the Apennine Sibyl really is.

The first clues that hinted to that process were the magical bridge and doors which were staged by Antoine de la Sale in his famous account of a visit to the Sibyl's cave: the two literary elements were taken from different, much more antique traditions, and included integrally in his narrative, as we have shown in previous dedicated papers (*Antoine de la Sale and the Magical Bridge Concealed beneath Mount Sibyl* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl - The Literary Truth about the Magical Doors Set beneath Mount Sibyl*).

Fig. 89 - The magical bridge as portrayed in Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château - Musée Condé, Chantilly, France, folium 10v)

Then, we found other clues, though pertaining to a different aspect of the concealing layers we intend to remove: we found a number of narrative elements added to *Guerrino the Wretch* that seem to have been taken from

earlier chivalric romances, none of them pertaining to stories set in the Sibillini Mountain Range.

For instance, in *Huon d'Auvergne* we found an episode concerning an oracular, necromantic, utterly wise lady associated to a mountain, to whom the knight hero is introduced by three damsels, with the hero lured into sin through illusory visions of charming beauty. This is a passage that Andrea da Barberino knew very well, as he reported it in his own version of *Huon* written in Italian: *Ugone d'Avernia*. Did Andrea da Barberino copied his wicked Sibyl from the necromantic dame which appears in *Huon d'Auvergne* and his own *Ugone*? Maybe. And similarities are not over at all, we can find many other remarkable resemblances.

In *Huon of Bordeaux* and *Ugone d'Avernia* we retrieve a passage in which the main character makes a journey to Rome to have his sins forgiven, depicted with words which closely resemble the similar descriptions contained in *Guerrino the Wretch* and the *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*.

Fig. 90 - The knight's visit to the Pope from Antoine de la Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl* (manuscript no. 0653 (0924), Bibliothèque du Château - Musée Condé, Chantilly, France, folium 17r)

In *Ugone d'Avernia* and *Guerrino the Wretch* we stumble upon a same episode involving the knight hero and one or more hermits, bearing a cross in their hands. In *Ugone d'Avernia*, the main character travels to the Italian

province of Calabria to retrieve information on the location of the entryway to Hell: a questions similar to that posed by the knight hero in *Guerrino the Wretch*, in the very same province of Calabria, as to the location of the Sibyl. In *Clariss et Laris*, a fairy damsel helps the main characters out of the enchanted realms in which they are confined: the same kind of helping hand in similar occurrences is lent to both Guerrino in *Guerrino the Wretch* and Lancelot in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*.

Furthermore, we found out, as scholars know well already, that the cave of the Apennine Sibyl is not the one and only example of a concealed place, sheltered from view and sometimes located underground or associated to a mountain, featuring beautiful gardens and magnificent palaces, and inhabited by a malign entity, often a sort of dark lady, often offering forbidden pleasures to visitors. We retrieved this narrative scheme in *Huon d'Auvergne*, *Ugone d'Avernia*, *The High History of the Holy Grail*, *Clariss et Laris*.

So we decided that the time was ripe for heading a new, daring course in our search for removing all additional leaves which conceal the true core of the Apennine Sibyl's legend: we elevated the narrative scheme of the enchanted realm - a major feature in the legend - to the rank of potential candidate for removal, with clear signs that it might just be a suggestive but extraneous medieval addition. With an extraneous Sibyl in it.

Fig. 91 - The crowned peak of Mount Sibyl in the Sibillini Mountain Range

Because something even more astounding happens in that same *Huon of Bordeaux*: in a magical castle guarded by an ever-moving device (reminiscent of Antoine de la Sale's magical doors) we find a young lady. Whose name is «Sebile», the ancient French word for Sibyl.

The coincidence is striking. Amid a plethora of medieval names potentially assigned to a dame living in an enchanted place, the unknown author of *Huon* selects exactly «Sibyl».

And something even more astounding occurs in *Claris et Laris*: the lady inside the enchanted castle, featuring the usual damsels and gardens and riches, is Morgan le Fay.

The final strike is provided by *Floriant et Florète*, another chivalric romance: here too there is a lady, and she rules an enchanted realm set beneath a mountain. An Italian mountain, Mount Etna, in Sicily. And - again - she is Morgan.

Morgan le Fay, King Arthur's sister. A main character of the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle.

So we found ourselves with Sibyl, Sebile and Morgan. All connected to enchanted realms, sharing similar characters.

Fig. 92 - Sibilla from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (edition printed in Venice in 1480), Sebile from the *Prophécies de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 25434, British Library, folium 173r), Morgan the Fay from *Lestoire de Merlin* (manuscript Additional MS 10292, British Library, folium 177r)

Then we started investigating the figure and literary traits of Morgan le Fay, who has been the object of extensive research by modern scholars: she is an oracle, healer and magician described for the first time by Geoffrey of

Monmouth, and associated with the enchanted island of Avalon, a land of blessing, in which King Arthur is still living an eternal life.

Has Morgan anything to do with Sibyls?

Yes indeed. A direct relationship among them was established in the twelfth century by Hartmann von Aue in his poem *Erec*, in which he described Morgan le Fay as a most powerful, evil magician. Just as a powerful as a Sibyl, writes von Aue (possibly the classical Cumaean, owing to necromantic tradition associated with her).

And the findings are not over. We discovered that Morgan le Fay was linked not only to a mythical island, Avalon, but also to some sort of mythical mountain. It was Mount Etna in *Florient et Florète*. And a mountain also appeared in Wolfram von Eschenbach's *Parzival*, in which Morgan le Fay is said to come from a special mountain, a fairy place, a Land of Joy.

In addition to that, we found out that in *Lestoire de Merlin* and *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* Morgan le Fay was also described as a wise lady, a savant, and - a new unprecedented trait - as a most sensual woman, «the most ardent woman in all Britain, and the most lecherous».

We began to recognize that since the Middle Ages Morgan le Fay and the Apennine Sibyl had started to share many common features: the rule over an enchanted realm; a wide and extensive knowledge of magical arts; impressive necromantic powers; a special mountain associated with them; a tendency to sexual desire; a land of bliss or joy.

And the resemblances continued to pour over. Morgan le Fay also showed an inclination for confining knights in her enchanted abode, just like the Apennine Sibyl. In *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, she casts a spell over a valley in which she holds knights in captivity: the Valley of No Return, a blissful place where to enjoy life, yet nonetheless a prison. A same place she creates in *Le Livre d'Artus*, in which knights can enter but are not allowed to leave.

But our amazing story goes even further. As Morgan le Fay seems gradually to converge on the Apennine Sibyl, the Sibyl too appears to take some steps in the direction of Morgan's.

In *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac*, we find right away a «Sebile» as a member of Morgan's party of fairies. And - again - it is said that both are the most powerful magicians in the world as to enchantments. Morgan, Sebile and a third fay forcibly abduct Lancelot to their castle, thus confirming their common bent to seize and confine knights for tempting them into sin.

And what does Lancelot tell the sensual ladies? He says «my name is Lancelot of the Lake the Wretch». He spells the very same adjective which will be used by Andrea da Barberino as an epithet for his knight hero Guerrino.

Fig. 93 - Guerrino gets the nickname of «Meschino» or «The Wretch» from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (manuscript no. MA297, Biblioteca Civica Angelo Mai, Bergamo, Italy, chapter VII); the same nickname is assigned by Lancelot to himself in *Le Livre de Lancelot del Lac* (manuscript Additional MS 10293, British Library, folium 282r)

And «Sebile the enchantress» is staged again in the *Prophécies de Merlin*, always as a mate of Morgan le Fay; and again in *Huon of Bordeaux* within a magical castle guarded by magical metal devices; and again in *La Chanson d'Esclarmonde*, together with Morgan, both living under a mountain in a realm of perfect joy and neverending youth.

We also find Sebile in a final, acrobatical transformation into Morgan herself: this happens in the *Wartburgkrieg*, which stages a Sibyl's child as the queen of the enchanted realm where King Arthur lives his eternal life, a role that is traditionally bestowed to Morgan le Fay.

And, in the *Wartburgkrieg*, the enchanted realm is set beneath a mountain.

We finally arrived to literary instances providing a clear, amazing evidence of an on-going combination between the figures of Morgan le Fay and the Apennine Sibyl, with a sort of full interchangeability between the two.

Just around fifty years before the appearance of a Sibyl of the Apennines, in *Ly Myreur des Histors* it's Morgan who presides over a Castle of Leisure, containing all sort of gardens, precious stones and treasures, and a court of charming, voluptuous damsels, wishing for enjoyment and apparently untouched by sin; yet the whole place is the product of Morgan's enchantments, and everything there is but illusion. There, knights lose all memories of the outer world, and live happily in eternal youth amid all sort of pleasures. And in *Perceforest*, it's the Sebile who rules an invisible castle, sheltered from view by magic, from which nobody can enter nor leave, in which a knight can become forgetful of time and outer world. And this Sibyl's castle, by the way, is not in the Apennines, but in Britain.

Clues, hints, evidences, manifest connections: all that we retrieved from the ancient manuscripts which hand over to us the literary tradition of Middle Ages chivalry show that Morgan le Fay, an antique, fundamental character of the Arthurian cycle, and the fifteenth-century Apennine Sibyl are closely connected to each other.

They are so strongly intertwined that one descends from the other.

The Apennine Sibyl appears to be the product of the transferral of Morgan le Fay's tradition and lore, already connected to Sibyls and Sebile, a fay and enchantress, from the Matter of Britain to a remote, mysterious peak which raises in the Italian Apennines.

Mount Sibyl has taken on itself an antique, much earlier legendary model outlined in previous centuries within a chivalric literary milieu, rooted in ancien Britain, France and Germany.

No Sibyl has ever resided beneath Mount Sibyl in Italy.

And that's the reason why, when querying the centuries which have preceded the fifteenth, no trace of an Apennine Sibyl could ever be found: there was no Apennine Sibyl to be spotted, neither in the Middle Ages nor

in Roman times. The only visible traces were the ones left by Morgan and her fairy companion Sebile.

Fig. 94 - One of the many fine miniatures included in manuscript Additional MS 10292 (folium 188r) preserved at the British Library in London, and containing the chivalric works *L'estoire del Saint Graal* and *L'estoire de Merlin*, superimposed to an evocative picture of Mount Sibyl

So, no Apennine Sibyl has ever existed.

Let's see in the next article whether this statement, of the utmost import and significance, can be finally and irrefutably confirmed, or not.

24. *The Apennine Sibyl, a shadow of Morgan le Fay*

In our previous series of article *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*, we wrote that «the Apennine Sibyl, who suddenly popped up during the fifteenth century in the works by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale, seems to have originated almost from nothing, as a sailing ship emerging all of a sudden from the thick mists which enshroud the sea, with all its masts and yards and rigs shining with bright, ominous light».

However, this occurred because at the beginning of our investigation we were looking for potential footsteps left through literary history by a Sibyl of the Apennines, and there are no such footsteps, because no Apennine Sibyl ever existed in both the medieval and Roman ages.

Fig. 95 - An artist's impression of a sailing ship emerging from thick mist, as the Apennine Sibyl did at the beginning of the fifteenth century (composite image by the author)

Instead, we found lots of traces, plenty of footsteps, and a true wealth of clear and manifest evidences that the legendary tale of the Apennine Sibyl descends in actual reality from an earlier literary tradition: that of Morgan le Fay, a prominent figure of the chivalric Matter of Britain, whose lore is closely connected to classical Sibyls and their skills as sorceresses and necromancers, with the personification of this connection embodied by a character named Sebile, a close intimate of Morgan in many chivalric poems and romances and often fully interchangeable with Arthur's sister in her role as dark queen of magically enchanted places.

So we can confidently repeat our momentous statement: no Sibyl has ever resided beneath Mount Sibyl in Italy.

The Apennine Sibyl is the result of a transplant of a different, extraneous legend into a specific Italian mountain, set amid the central Apennines in the land of Italy. An adaptation of British, French and German lore concerning Morgan le Fay and her friend Sebile, a distant descendant of classical Sibyls, to a peculiar place lost amid the remote fastnesses of what we call today the Sibillini Mountain Range.

The Apennine Sibyl is nothing more than one of the additional layers which conceal the true origin of the Italian legend. A layer that needed to be removed.

Just a crazy idea? A whimsical surmise, only supported by flimsy resemblances between two different literary characters - Morgan le Fay and the Apennine Sibyl - who have nothing to do one another?

Is all that a mere fancy proposed by an imaginative researcher with a nice, yet totally unfounded paper?

The answer is no. Because many other professional scholars have elaborated on that same idea: the Apennine Sibyl, as the product of a different tradition, to be retrieved amid earlier chivalric romances, in connection with the literary traits typically associated with Morgan le Fay, as reported by Maria Luciana Buseghin in her comprehensive essay *L'Ultima Sibilla (The Last Sibyl)* published in 2012.

Already in 1903, Lucy Ann Paton, in her “Studies in the fairy mythology of Arthurian romance”, wrote that «as a rule she [Sebile the enchantress] is merely a shadow of Morgain», and that both “Guerrino the Wretch” and “The Paradise of Queen Sibyl” are «sources [which] supplement each other, Antoine's representing purer Celtic material, Andrea's preserving more distinctly the Sibylline character of the fay [...] Both sources show tendencies that are often displayed in mediaeval fairy lore [...] with] the merging of Celtic and classical tradition in popular story».

Fig. 96 - Lucy Ann Paton's passage on Sebile contained in *Studies in the fairy mythology of Arthurian romance*, Boston, 1903 (pages 52 and 53, footnote no. 2)

The Italian scholar Ferdinando Neri, in his *Le tradizioni italiane della Sibilla* (*The Italian traditions of the Sibyl*) (1913), writes that «the Sibyl's paradise must be linked to the enchanted lands [...] In chivalric poems, this is the land of fairies, the realm of Morgan, Avalon [...] Sibyl: that was a name of a fairy, always mentioned in conjunction with Morgan [in other chivalric works]» [in the original Italian text: «Il paradiso della Sibilla deve allora porsi a riscontro delle terre incantate [...] Nella poesia cavalleresca è la terra di féerie, il regno di Morgana, Avalon [...] Sibilla: questo era un nome di fata, e sempre insieme con Morgana appare [in varie opere cavalleresche]»].

However, the most significant confirmation to the model we are currently proposing as to the chivalric origin of the Apennine Sibyl is provided by a great scholar and illustrious professor, one of the most prominent authorities in the literary tradition of Middle Ages, the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle.

Fig. 97 - The excerpt on Sibyl from Ferdinando Neri's *Le tradizioni italiane della Sibilla* (in *Studi medievali*, Torino, 1912-1913, page 228)

His name is Roger S. Loomis. And he wrote a scientific paper in which he stated with exact precision this same point: the Apennine Sibyl is the product of an adaptation of Morgan le Fay's tradition and lore to a specific location set in the central Apennines of Italy.

Fig. 98 - Roger Sherman Loomis

Let's see in the next article what Professor Loomis, a famed, celebrated member of the Columbia University, had to say about *Guerrino the Wretch* and *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*. And about the Sibyl of the Apennines.

25. *The Sibyl of the Apennines and her lineage from King Arthur's fairy sister*

In 1959, Roger Sherman Loomis wrote a fundamental essay, *Morgain la Fée in oral tradition*, which has remained substantially unknown to the various Italian researchers who have been investigating into the myth of the Apennine Sibyl in the subsequent decades, as it is almost never quoted in the books and papers issued in Italy on the subject since its first publication.

Fig. 99 - Roger S. Loomis' paper on *Morgain la Fée in oral tradition* (from *Romania*, tome LXXX, no. 319, Paris, 1959, pages 337-367)

This is a most exciting piece of scientific inference produced by a great, knowledgeable scholar, an utmost authority in the Matter of Britain. And his conclusions are perfectly identical to the results obtained by the author of this paper, who discovered Loomis' article towards the end of his own search, and therefore was not influenced by the position expressed by the illustrious scholar on the subject.

Roger S. Loomis totally corroborates the very same framework we have been drawing in the present paper: the origin of the myth of an Apennine Sibyl is not to be retrieved in the Italian Apennines, as this Sibyl is the product of a literary transplant of the legend of Morgan le Fay, and the enchantress Sebile, into a specific Italian setting, that of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

«The extraordinary account», writes Loomis, «given early in the fifteenth century by Andrea da Barberino of the visit of *Guerino il Meschino* to the abode of the fay Alcina [the name replacing the Sibyl in the 1689 edition - editor's note] [...] was actually an elaboration of a visit to the abode of Morgain la Fée. [...] Though the geographical setting on a mountain near Norcia in the central Apennines was described with accuracy, the main theme must have been taken from some version of the visit to Morgain's enchanted palace».

presented themselves to him as rivals for his love ². For there is striking evidence to show that Hartmann and the authors of the *Lancelot* and the *Prophecies de Merlin* were not the only ones to associate Morgain with the Sibyl; the extraordinary

account given early in the fifteenth century by Andrea da Barberino of the visit of *Guerino il Meschino* to the abode of the fay Alcina, who incidentally revealed herself as the Sibyl who had given Aeneas a vision of Anchises, was actually an elaboration of a visit to the abode of Morgain la Fée. Though Andrea borrowed many details from Dante, the *Fatti d'Enea* of Guido da Pisa, and one of his own works, *Ugone d'Alvernia* ¹, and though the geographical setting on a mountain near Norcia in the central Apennines was described with accuracy, the main theme must have been taken from some version of the visit to Morgain's enchanted palace. A comparison of an episode in

Fig. 100 - The words by Roger S. Loomis on *Guerrino the Wretch* in *Morgain la Fée* in oral tradition (from *Romania*, tome LXXX, no. 319, Paris, 1959, pages 347-348)

So, according to Loomis, who perfectly knew all the literary excerpts we have proposed to the reader's attention in our present work, the Apennine Sibyl is just an offspring of a more illustrious literary tradition concerning Morgan le Fay. We totally agree with Loomis on that, and we also agree to his further elaboration on the issue:

«In spite of the obvious changes and literary embellishments, the account of Guerino's visit to the Sibyl's sensual Paradise is manifestly derived from some version of Morgain's faery Paradise not unlike that described in "Clariss et Laris". [...] Alcina's nature is best explained, then, as uniting characteristic features of Morgain and the Sibyl».

conducts him to the door by which he entered. He travels to Rome, confesses to the Pope, and is granted absolution.

In spite of the obvious changes and literary embellishments, the account of Guerino's visit to the Sibyl's sensual Paradise is manifestly derived from some version of Morgain's faery Paradise not unlike that described in *Clariss et Laris*. In both tales the beautiful fay who presides over the enchanted realm welcomes the hero or heroes and endeavors to hold them in her power; she is attended by charming damsels; there is an

l'Orphelin *. Alcina's nature is best explained, then, as uniting characteristic features of Morgain and the Sibyl: like the former she is a beautiful temptress, whose efforts to keep her victims perpetually in thrall are thwarted by one of her damsels; like the latter she dwells in a cave and possesses preternatu-

Fig. 101 - The Apennine Sibyl and Morgan as seen by Roger S. Loomis in *Morgain la Fée in oral tradition* (from *Romania*, tome LXXX, no. 319, Paris, 1959, page 350)

Furthermore, Loomis clearly shows the correct way to rebut a trivial criticism that might be opposed to the substantial identification of the Apennine Sibyl with Morgan le Fay: how can an Arthurian cycle's traditional character have moved from Old Britain as far as central Italy?

The answer is quite natural: this is exactly what occurred in actual reality as attested by unquestionable proofs, well-known among scholars:

«If it seems difficult to believe that the legends of Morgain and her enchanted valley were transferred to a mountain in central Italy, let us remember that the tradition of Arthur's survival in the blissful isle of

Avalon, over which Morgan presided, was carried even farther and was attached to Mount Etna».

ral knowledge. If it seems difficult to believe that the legends of Morgain and her enchanted valley were transferred to a mountain in central Italy, let us remember that the tradition of Arthur's survival in the blissful isle of Avalon, over which Morgain presided, was carried even farther and was attached to Mount Etna.

Fig. 102 - Migration of arthurian tales from Britain to Italy analysed in Loomis' *Morgain la Fée in oral tradition* (from *Romania*, tome LXXX, no. 319, Paris, 1959, page 350)

So, the Arthurian legends lived and thrived among readers and oral audiences in Italy, as is attested by the very fortune of Andrea da Barberino's chivalric romances, written in Italian for the enjoyment of people living in the Italian peninsula. And in Italy this diffusion process was already active well before Andrea began to write his works, on an oral, uncheckable basis, as Loomis effectively points out:

«There must have been a prodigious circulation of tales about the fairy queen by word of mouth, partly in elaborate forms devised by professional entertainers, and partly in the simpler forms of local gossip and travelers' yarns», as it would be «to fly in the face of the evidence to deny the power and persistence of oral tradition in fashioning the Matière de Bretagne».

The Arthurian Cycle, moving from Britain and travelling through France and Germany, was circulating across Italy in the form of both chivalric romances and oral storytelling, played in public squares, at the corners of streets, in village fairs and open-air markets, during town festivals, and even in the occasion of the most important religious festivities.

Macha on the other. If the facts presented in this article can stand critical examination, there must have been a prodigious circulation of tales about the fairy queen by word of mouth, partly in elaborate forms devised by professional entertainers, and partly in the simpler forms of local gossip and travelers' yarns. By no manner of means could these multifarious traditions have developed from the earliest references to her in literature — Geoffrey of Monmouth's *Vita Merlini*, Benoît de

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ing from earlier literary sources, or to deny that there are some Arthurian romances (e. g. *Cligès*, *Gliglois*, *Estoire del Saint Graal*) which owe almost nothing to the *conteurs*; that would be to fly in the face of the evidence. But it is also to fly in the face of the evidence to deny the power and persistence of oral tradition in fashioning the *Matière de Bretagne*.

Roger S. LOOMIS.

Fig. 103 - Storytelling and chivalric tales as seen by Roger S. Loomis in *Morgain la Fée in oral tradition* (from *Romania*, tome LXXX, no. 319, Paris, 1959, pages 366-367)

«Whether Andrea da Barberino himself», continues Loomis, «was responsible for this fusion of the Sibyl and Morgain into one person and for localizing Morgain's paradise in the Monte della Sibilla, it is impossible to say [...] We see, too, from the testimony of contemporary writers that these developments were largely an oral phenomenon, and that it was only after the legends had been the subject of popular rumor and perhaps professional recitation that literary men set them down and elaborated them on parchment».

Roger S. Loomis could not have been more limpid than that. If we want to comprehend the literary origin of a figure such as the Apennine Sibyl we must turn to Morgan le Fay and the world in which her tradition has undergone centuries of elaborations, modifications and adaptations. A world made of chivalric romances and poems, professional storytellers who travelled from one place to another across Europe, and a mighty oral process by which the Matter of Britain has been handed over to a countless number of different communities, cultural settings and local geographical environments, with a continual transformation of themes and traits under a

common narrative framework, fully capable of adapting itself to the needs, tastes and expectations of each single audience.

Whether Andrea da Barberino himself was responsible for this fusion of the Sibyl and Morgain into one person and for localizing Morgain's paradise in the Monte della Sibilla, it is impossible to say; but it is highly probable that his activity as a *cantatore* did much to give the legend a vogue. For when Antoine de la Sale, the Provençal tutor of Prince John of Calabria, made a pilgrimage to the mountain in 1420, he seems

Thus we see how an originally Breton legend of Morgain's Paradise of amorous pleasures was transferred in Italy to the Sibyl, because Morgain, like the Sibyl, could foretell the future; and how, in turn, this Italian legend was transferred by Germans to Venus, because the presiding genius of the Monte della Sibilla retained too much of the lascivious nature of her Breton original to comport well with the established character of the Sibyl. We see, too, from the testimony of contemporary writers that these developments were largely an oral phenomenon, and that it was only after the legends had been the subject of popular rumor and perhaps of professional recitation that literary men set them down and elaborated them on parchment.

Fig. 104 - Andrea da Barberino, Morgan, the Apennine Sibyl and oral recitation in *Morgain la Fée in oral tradition* (from *Romania*, tome LXXX, no. 319, Paris, 1959, pages 350 and 352)

So, this long phase of our search into the true core of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl is nearly completed. However, we still need to say a few final words.

A few words, which are needed to end this thrilling, amazing journey into the world of chivalry. And to start a new extraordinary search which will bring us at a fingertip's distance from the very nature of the sibilline lore. Which is still to be unveiled.

26. *Is the Apennine Sibyl dead?*

When we started our daring search into the true origin of the Apennine Sibyl's legend, we wrote that we wanted to remove all literary additions conferred to her legendary tale throughout the centuries, and take off all the concentric layers and sheltering leaves that encircle and suffocate the true

mythical nucleus, with the aim of cleaning her figure by wiping out the narrative elements that have been added with time to her story, borrowed from several different mythical tales.

We wanted to dispel the impenetrable mist that had accompanied her sudden appearance at the beginning of the fifteenth century, when two authors, Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale, wrote in their works of a Sibyl who had her abode in a secluded mountainous region of central Apennines in Italy.

Now, such literary additions and concentric layers and sheltering leaves have been wiped out, together with the inscrutable fog which concealed the real lineage of that Sibyl. A Sibyl that comes out from a long, antique tradition concerning Morgan le Fay and the chivalric tales which are part of the Matter of Britain.

We are now able to provide an answer to many (but not to all, as we will see below) of the questions we had posed at the very beginning of our investigation.

Did the tradition concerning an Apennine Sibyl living beneath Mount Sibyl actually emerge, as a fully original, native tale, from the Italian Sibillini Mountain Range? The answer is no, as the Sibyl shows a marked, unmistakable influence from the world of chivalric literature and lore, and a specific lineage from a main character belonging to the Arthurian Cycle, Morgan le Fay.

Was the Apennine Sibyl's legend truly generated in the region of Mount Sibyl, or was it transplanted there from some different cultural areas and geographic territories into that specific, particular spot of land? It is positively so, as we saw that this Sibyl is the final outcome of an evolutionary process which settled eventually down in the area that is known today under the name of Sibillini Mountain Range.

Has the Apennine Sibyl really journeyed a long way across the centuries and through that inscrutable fog, after having started her travel in ancient times and having remained unseen until she emerged in the fifteenth century? In a sense, yes. However, the travelling Sibyl was not from the Apennines, instead she was a character belonging to both a literary and oral

tradition whose ancestor was Morgan le Fay, a figure in close association with Sibyls and subsequently transformed into a fay called Sebile. Because Morgan le Fay and her mate have left lots of footprints throughout the entire history of chivalric literature, showing significant similarities between them and the Apennine Sibyl: a number of scattered, interspersed literary evidencies which totally confirm this scenario.

Was the Apennine Sibyl the most recent product of some strange condensation of that thick, whirling mist, in which her myth took form not in antiquity, but just very close to the beginning of the fifteenth century? Yes, to some extent. The Apennine Sibyl is probably born from oral tradition somewhere in the fourteenth century, and not much afterwards she has been represented and has stabilized herself in literary works such as “Guerrino the Wretch” and “The Paradise of Queen Sibyl”. Nonetheless, the whirling mist from which she originated already contained, in previous centuries, her foremothers, Morgan and Sebile.

Fig. 105 - The image we presented in the initial paragraph of the present article *The Apennine Sibyl: a journey into history in search of the oracle*, now completed with the footsteps left by the Sibyl as Morgan's companion (composite image by the author)

And, at this point of our enquiry, we can re-draw the picture we already proposed at the very start of our investigation, by filling up the voids in the cloud with the insertion of the travelling footprints of the Sibyl (Sibilla, Sebile, Sibillen, Seville), crossing the centuries and emerging finally in the early fifteenth century, with the works by Andrea da Barberino and Antoine de la Sale: a long journey, at the end of which the Apennine Sibyl stands out from the darkness of history with all her splendour.

However, is that all?

Are we treading a path that is leading to a sad final destination merely consisting in a sorrowful 'downgrade' of the Apennine Sibyl, from an independent, original myth to a sheer adaptation of legends developed elsewhere?

Are we just saying that this Sibyl is a sort of 'fake' myth, now stripped off of all its shining chivalric package, and exposed in its nakedness as an empty container of a legendary tale which belongs to other countries, other people, other illustrious mythical traditions, namely those pertaining to the Matter of Britain?

Is that the end of the legend of a Sibyl of the Apennines?

No. This is not the end. An enigma still thrives, with a dark, sinister glow, over the remote peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range. At the very center of Italy.

As we will see in the next, conclusive article.

27. The enigma still lies there amid the mountains

In our previous article, we presented the conclusions of our long study on the true origin of the legend of the Apennine Sibyl.

The results show that the Sibyl of the Apennines descends from an illustrious lineage of fays portrayed in the Matter of Britain. Most likely she is the adaptation of the characters of Morgan le Fay and Sebile to a specific Italian setting, that of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

A lineage that seems to turn into an almost tangible manifestation when we open one of the most ancient versions available of *Guerrino the Wretch*, contained in manuscript no. MA297 preserved at the Biblioteca Civica *Angelo Mai* in Bergamo, Italy. In this version, dating to 1468, the Apennine Sibyl is not indicated with the usual Italian word 'Sibilla', which we find in later printed editions, but as «Sibilia»: an unusual name whose Italian spelling is remarkably similar to that of the French word 'Sebile'.

Fig. 106 - The Apennine Sibyl as «Sibilia» from Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (manuscript no. MA297, Biblioteca Civica *Angelo Mai*, Bergamo, Italy, Chapter CLIII)

Morgan, Sebile, Sibilia, the Sibyl of the Apennines. A line of descent that will certainly need further study, yet we think that the present research, noteworthy supported by similar conclusions drawn in the past by Roger S. Loomis, may provide the right trail we need to tread if we want to fully understand the ancient mystery and illustrious tradition concerning this Italian Sibyl.

However, this is not the end of the Apennine Sibyl's legend. Not in the least.

Because Morgan and Sebile, fascinating figures as they are, are not enough to explain why it all happened.

Her enigma, the enigma of the Sibyl of the Apennines, is everything but solved.

Because still we have not answered two fundamental questions, the most critical amid those we stated at the very beginning of our search: did the Apennine Sibyl arise from some odd condensation of any peculiar nature of that place, the Sibillini Mountain Range? Was the original core of the Apennine Sibyl's legend born there, owing to the fact that that location was some sort of very special site?

As we said, we know for certain that the Sibyl of the Apennines was shaped around additional mythical themes taken from other tales and stories, namely the Matter of Britain and the Arthurian cycle. However, why such tales and stories did elect to stop exactly there, amid the peaks of the Sibillini Mountain Range?

Morgan the Fay, Sebile the enchantress, the magically narrow bridge, the ever-slamming doors, the oracular site, the visits to a hidden subterranean realm: why all this extraordinary narrative settled down precisely in that spot, lost amid the mountainous fastnesses of the Italian Apennines?

No scholar has ever addressed this issue. We find no answers on that in Roger S. Loomis, Lucy Ann Paton, Ferdinando Neri, nor in any other scholars. No research paper has ever dealt with this fundamental question.

The legendary narrative material belonging to the lore of Morgan and the Sibyls might as well have landed at any other location in Italy or elsewhere, depositing its mythical charge in a different place, so as to set up a brand new legend concerning an enchanted paradise in Tuscany, or Piedmont, or Sicily, as it actually happened at Mount Etna, or even Sardinia. Anywhere else.

But the legend established itself right here: in the middle of the Sibillini Mountain Range.

What sort of magnetic pull did attract the magical tales of the Arthurian cycle on the sinister peak of Mount Sibyl? For what kind of fated chance did the Matter of Britain come to rest, like a ball spinning on a roulette wheel, right into the position marked by this remote Italian mountain?

The land of Italy is scattered of hundreds of peaks and mountaintops: why weren't they fit to house a legend on fays and enchanted realms?

Why Mount Sibyl?

Our thrilling enquiry is not over. We have unfolded the heavy chivalric layer which sheltered from view the inner, most genuine core of the Apennine Sibyl's legend. We have found Morgan le Fay and Sebile. But, still, we have not reached the true nucleus of the myth.

There is something more to it. Something sinister, something obscure which has magnetized all that mythical might, both literary and oral, onto that specific place of Earth: an Italian mountain, lost in the middle of the Apennines.

Fig. 107 - A peak and a mystery: Mount Sibyl

We need to go further. We need to fully unfold the residual additions that still conceal the main, focal point of the legend of Mount Sibyl. The point from which it all began.

Our work is not finished yet. The mystery is not still solved. The enigma still lies there.

Because the legend of the Apennine Sibyl is not dead at all. We want to clutch her ultimate secret in our hands. We want to find out who she really is.

The hunt for the Sibyl of the Apennines is not over.

And we are now ready, as we will see in a further series of article we will soon publish, for the final, decisive step.

A step that will unveil the very nature, and the true semblance, of the Sibyl of the Apennines.

Michele Sanvico

END OF PART 2

**Please refer to Part 1
for the first section of the research paper**